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Editor
R.K. Verma

Indian Institute of Public Administration

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Dr. R.K. Verma

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Bihar Regional Branch

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E-GOVERNANCE ADAPTATION: A STUDY OF USER PERCEPTIONS AND SATISFACTION IN THE THIRUVANANTHAPURAM MUNICIPAL CORPORATION, KERALA

Saurabh Chandra*

Abstract

In this age of IR 4.0 digitalisation in governance has become essential. This has made an urgent imperative to assess the adaptation of e-governance in urban administration in terms of perception and satisfaction of the users. As such an attempt has been made to examine the e-governance services offered by the Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation. It is mainly based on empirical enquiry. A survey with the help of structured questionnaire was conducted, 200 users, falling in the municipal areas, were sampled, in order to find out the influence of demographic variables, including gender, age, education, and sector of employment, on users' perceptions and satisfaction. The findings revealed that the Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation has not fully attained the goals of e-governance adaptation, particularly in terms of enhancing Transparency, Accountability, and Participation. However, the overall satisfaction level with e-governance services remains encouraging.

Keywords: E-Governance; User Perceptions; Satisfaction; Municipal Corporations; Kerala

INTRODUCTION

E-governance and Democratic Decentralization share a similar vision. The concept of 'Democratic Decentralization' involves democratisation and the development of grassroots governance close to citizens and aims to ensure efficient and effective delivery of public services through local government institutions (Singh, Pathak, Naz, & Belwal, 2010, pp. 254-275).

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In India, with the implementation of the 74th Constitutional Amendment Act of 1993, local government institutions were constitutionally empowered for urban areas. This marked the adoption of the decentralization vision, which includes deepening democracy, ensuring citizen participation, enhancing accountability and transparency, and improving public service efficiency. These expectations align with what citizens anticipate from decentralized local government institutions (Aijaz, 2007; Keivani, 2009).

To address these challenges, e-governance has been purposely adopted in Municipal Corporations across India (Yadav, 2009, pp. 679-692; Anudeep Rawal, 2011; Dwivedi & Bharti, 2014; Ilangovan & Meena, 2016; Samuel, Doctor, Christian, & Baradi, 2020, pp. 408-417; NITI Aayog, 2021; Tejedó-Romero, Araujo, Tejada, & Ramírez, 2022). Consequently, this study aims to assess the extent to which Municipal Corporations in India have achieved the goals of e-governance adaptation. Therefore, the study analyses users' perceptions and levels of satisfaction with the e-governance services provided by the Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation. Additionally, the study seeks to identify how demographic variables affect users' perceptions and levels of satisfaction with e-governance services. Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation was chosen for the study due to the researcher's convenience. Additionally, Thiruvananthapuram, the capital city of the Indian state of Kerala, possesses unique geographic, demographic, and cultural attributes that render it an intriguing area for this type of research. Its diverse population, urban development, and historical significance could be of particular interest. The findings of research conducted in a municipal corporation like Thiruvananthapuram may have policy implications at the local, regional, or national level, making it a suitable location for research.

OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

It aims to assess the perception and evaluate user satisfaction with the e-governance services offered by the Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation (TMC). Thereby, mark the influence of of demographic variables on user perceptions and satisfaction levels.

Three locations of the TMC namely Vazhuthacaud, Palayam, and Cherunniyoor were selected and from there 200 user respondents were randomly sampled and interviewed. In addition, the researcher also approached the Janasevanakendrams and Akshaya Centers in these areas. The survey was conducted from mid-February 2019 to the last week of May 2019. In Thiruvananthapuram, interviews were conducted with 95 males and 105 females who met the inclusion criteria of the study. The profile of the respondents is given below in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Statistics of the Respondents

<i>Demographic Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>%</i>
Gender		
Male	95	47.5%
Female	105	52.5%
Age		
18-30 (Years)	57	28.5%
31-40 (Years)	81	40.5%
41-50 (Years)	49	24.5%
>50 (Years)	13	6.5%
Educational level		
Higher or less	14	7.0%
Intermediate	70	35.0%
Graduation	75	37.5%
Post-graduation	37	18.5%
Above Post-graduation	4	2.0%
Sector of Employment		
Currently Unemployed	54	27.0%
Non-Profit Sector	38	19.0%
Private Sector	79	39.5%
Public Sector	29	14.5%

(N = 200)

DATA ANALYSIS

Each dimension (transparency, accountability, and participation) of e-governance has been measured using the Likert scale rating from 1-strongly agree to disagree 5-strongly. The level of satisfaction has also been measured using the Likert scale rating from 1-Very satisfied to 5-Very dissatisfied. A Cronbach's coefficient alpha has been computed to assess the reliability of the items used in measuring the respondent's perception of three e-governance dimensions and their level of satisfaction and the result has been presented in Table 2. Testing the influence of respective variables on each e-governance dimension and level of satisfaction was carried out using the significance level of p-value = 0.05. Still, there is considered even other statistical value of 'p' to define the statistical influence of each variable on the dimension (p-value = 1% and 10%). A T-test was performed to determine whether Gender affects users' perceptions of the value of using e-government portals for citizen involvement and the level of satisfaction while the other demographic

was used one-way ANOVA. The SPSS software has been used to analyse data and to test the relationship between e-governance dimensions and other demographic variables.

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
0.737	0.736	4

There are considered N = 4 items (3 dimensions + 1 Level of satisfaction) to calculate three dimensions related to the perception of e-governance and one item related to their level of satisfaction. The Cronbach's alpha has a value considered good ($\alpha = 0.737$) that shows the reliability of items taken into consideration for calculation dimensions.

FINDING

To address the impact of gender on the perception and satisfaction on good governance, a T-Test was conducted to examine whether Gender has an impact on users' perceptions and their level of satisfaction. The results are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3: T-Test for users' perception and their level of satisfaction with e-governance by Gender

<i>E-governance Dimension</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>No.</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>T-Values</i>
Transparency	Male	95	3.0211	0.92229	1.215
	Female	105	2.8571	0.98477	
Accountability	Male	95	2.2211	0.93603	0.908
	Female	105	2.0952	1.02398	
Participation	Male	95	1.6105	0.67311	1.923**
	Female	105	1.4286	0.66299	
Level of Satisfaction	Male	95	3.3789	1.18662	0.815
	Female	105	3.2571	0.88826	

(The level of significance *p < 10% ** p < 5%, ***p < 1%)

Table 3 clearly demonstrates that, in all aspects of e-governance, namely transparency, accountability, and participation, males tend to have higher mean scores than females. The data reveals that there are no significant differences in transparency, accountability, and overall satisfaction, as indicated by p-values of 10%, whereas for participation, the difference is statistically significant at a 5% level. Notably, the discrepancy in mean satisfaction levels is particularly significant, with a considerably lower p-value compared to the other dimensions. However, for

accountability, despite the gender-based mean differences, the distinction is not statistically significant, with a p-value greater than 10%.

These findings indicate that male respondents perceive higher value across all dimensions of e-governance and report greater satisfaction with e-governance services compared to their female counterparts. Males exhibit a more favourable perception of transparency, accountability, and participation in the e-governance services provided by their Municipal Corporation. In contrast, female users express a stronger desire for increased transparency, accountability, and participation in these services. These results support the previous researches in which the male perceived a higher value of e-governance in comparison to females (Al-Shafi & Weerakkody, 2010; Al Athmay A.-A., 2013; Al-hashmi & Suresha, 2013; Al Athmay A., 2015) and also support the findings (Choudrie, Light, & Papazafeiropoulou, 2004; Jyoti & Yogesh, 2005; Choudrie & Dwivedi, 2005; Dwivedi & Williams, 2008, p. 261; Singh, Pathak, Naz, & Belwal, 2010, pp. 254-275; Mwakangala, 2012; Chandra, 2021) and indicate the impact of user's Gender on their perception and level of satisfaction with the e-governance services.

To find the impact of age factor, one-way analysis of variance was carried out to answer the second research question. Table 4 shows that there are significant differences in the perception and level of satisfaction based on the ages of the respondents on all dimensions of e-governance.

Table 4: One-way analysis of the Mean Difference in Users' perception and their level of satisfaction according to age

<i>E-governance dimension</i>	<i>18-30</i>	<i>31-40</i>	<i>41-50</i>	<i>>50</i>	<i>F</i>
	I	II	III	IV	
Transparency	3.16	2.78	2.90	3.08	1.906
Accountability	2.26	2.21	2.00	1.92	0.961
Participation	1.61	1.46	1.53	1.38	0.784
Level of Satisfaction	3.35	3.27	3.12	4.15	3.584**

(The level of significance *p < 10% ** p < 5%, ***p < 1%)

Table 4 clearly indicates that respondents between the ages of 18 and 30 hold a more favourable perception of all dimensions of e-governance compared to older age groups. There exists a significant relationship between the age groups of respondents and the dimensions of e-governance, as evidenced by a Fisher test with a p-value less than 10%. Respondents aged above 50 years exhibit a higher overall level of satisfaction with e-governance in comparison to younger age groups. The means across different age groups are statistically significant at a 5% level, indicating that age groups significantly influence the mean level of satisfaction.

The results indicate significant differences among age groups in all three dimensions of e-government. Respondents between the ages of 18 to 30 exhibit a more favourable perception of e-governance transparency, accountability, and participation when compared to older age groups. These results indicate that age may influence users' perceptions of e-governance dimensions. Users in the younger age group have a more favourable perception of e-governance compared to users in the older age group. A more favourable perception of e-governance dimensions among users in the younger age groups implies an association between respondents' age and their perception of e-governance dimensions. In other words, the younger the respondents, the more favourable their perception of these e-governance dimensions. These results suggest that age has an influence on users' perception and satisfaction levels regarding e-governance, which aligns with findings from previous studies (Choudrie & Dwivedi, 2005; Colesca & Dobrica, 2008; Dwivedi & Williams, 2008, p. 261; Mwakangala, 2012; Jun & Wang, 2012, pp. 25-27; Al Athmay A.-A., 2013; Al Athmay A., 2015; Chandra, 2021).

The impact of education factor was addressed. respondents were categorized based on their level of education, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to assess whether achieving a particular level of education influences users' perceptions of key dimensions of e-governance, namely transparency, accountability, participation, and their satisfaction with e-governance services. The results of this analysis are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: One-way analysis of the Mean Difference in Users' perception and level of satisfaction according to the educational level

<i>E-governance dimension</i>	<i>High School or below</i>	<i>Intermediate</i>	<i>Graduation</i>	<i>Post-Graduation</i>	<i>Above Post-graduation</i>	<i>F</i>
	<i>II</i>	<i>III</i>	<i>IV</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>VI</i>	
Transparency	2.29	3.17	2.83	2.95	3.00	3.047**
Accountability	1.43	2.41	1.99	2.30	2.00	4.146***
Participation	1.57	1.59	1.49	1.41	1.50	0.479
Level of satisfaction	3.00	3.37	3.17	3.54	4.00	1.609

(The level of significance *p < 10% ** p < 5%, ***p < 1%)

From Table 5, it is evident that:

- (a) the higher values for the e-governance dimensions of Transparency, Accountability, and Participation have been perceived by respondents with a lower level of education, i.e. intermediate or below.

- (b) The overall satisfaction level for all dimensions of e-governance is highest among respondents with a higher level of education, i.e. post-graduation and above.
- (c) The level of education significantly influences transparency at a p-value of 5% and accountability at a p-value of 1%.

These findings can be attributed to the elevated expectations of users with higher educational levels regarding e-governance. Individuals with higher educational levels anticipate greater transparency, increased accountability, and more opportunities for participation in e-governance. Nevertheless, they express higher overall satisfaction with e-governance services. The findings of the study may not align with those of previous studies, where users from higher educational levels perceived higher values in e-governance dimensions (Dwivedi & Williams, 2008, p. 261; Al-Shafi & Weerakkody, 2010; Al Athmay A.-A., 2013; Al Athmay A., 2015). However, it indicates that the educational level influences users' perceptions and levels of satisfaction with e-governance services. Table 5 clearly shows that users with a lower level of education, specifically those with intermediate education, have a highly positive perception of all aspects of e-governance. Among the 200 respondents in Thiruvananthapuram, 42.5% were categorized as intermediate or below in terms of education. These findings do not align with previous studies, which suggested that citizens with a higher level of education use e-services more frequently compared to those with lower levels of education (Al-hashmi & Suresha, 2013) (Belwal & Al-Zoubi, 2008, pp. 317-333).

To find the impact occupation, a T-Test was conducted, and the results have been displayed in Table 6. The results show the means of e-governance perception and the level of satisfaction based on the employment status of the respondents.

Table 6: T-Test for users' perception and their level of satisfaction with e-governance according to the sector of employment

<i>E-governance Dimension</i>	<i>Public Sector</i>	<i>Private Sector</i>	<i>Non-Profit sector</i>	<i>Currently Unemployed</i>	<i>T-Values</i>
Transparency	3.13	3.11	2.76	2.83	1.481*
Accountability	2.13	2.58	1.99	2.10	1.808**
Participation	1.44	1.63	1.53	1.45	0.829
Level of Satisfaction	3.44	3.50	3.11	3.38	1.312

(The level of significance *p < 10% ** p < 5%, ***p < 1%)

From Table 6, it is evident that:

- (a) Respondents employed in the public sector significantly perceive a higher value for the e-governance dimension "Transparency" at the 10% level.

- (b) Respondents employed in the private sector perceive a higher value for the e-governance dimensions of “Accountability” and “Participation.” Additionally, employees in the private sector express greater satisfaction with e-governance services compared to respondents employed in other sectors.

The results of this study indicate that public sector employees value transparency in e-governance, while private sector employees prioritize accountability and participation, both crucial for effective e-governance. These results indicate the impact of user’s employment sector on their perception and satisfaction levels with e-governance services, confirming the findings of previous studies (Choudrie & Dwivedi, 2005; Al Athmay A.-A., 2013; Al Athmay A., 2015; Chandra, 2021). This study also confirms the previous findings (Al-hashmi & Suresha, 2013), which suggest that the majority of the population using e-services is employed. This study observed that 73% of the population that has ever used e-services is employed.

To address the fifth and final research question, the overall mean value of the respondents’ perceptions across the three dimensions of E-governance and satisfaction was calculated. The results are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: The overall Mean Value of the Respondents to the three dimensions of E-governance and level of satisfaction

<i>E-governance Dimension</i>	<i>Mean Ranking</i>
Transparency	2.94
Accountability	2.16
Participation	1.52
Level of Satisfaction	3.32

1-2 Unfavourable; 2-3 Less favourable; 3-4 Favourable; 4-5 More Favourable.

Table 7 indicates the mean values for two dimensions of e-governance: transparency and accountability, both of which fall within the range of 2 and 3. These values suggest a less favourable value. The less favourable values in these dimensions point to ongoing challenges with transparency and accountability in the e-governance services offered by the Municipal Corporation. Furthermore, the table also demonstrates that the mean value for the dimension of participation is unfavourable. This indicates a significant issue with participation in the Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation.

This confirms previous studies that have raised concerns about transparency, accountability, and participation in the service delivery of urban local bodies (Aijaz, 2007; Rao & Prasad, 2007; Vaidya, 2009; Coelho, Kamath, & Vijaybaskar, 2011; Sharma, 2012; Singh S., 2013; Siwach & Nillam, 2014; Ahluwalia, Kanbur, & Mohanty, 2017; Bhide, 2017; Ahluwalia, 2019; Chakrabarty & Pandey, 2019; Samuel, Doctor, Christian, & Baradi, 2020, pp. 408-417; NITI Aayog, 2021). However, the mean value for the level of satisfaction falls between 3 and 4 (specifically 3.32),

suggesting that users' perceptions of the various dimensions of e-governance may be unfavourable for participation and somewhat less favourable for transparency and accountability. Nevertheless, users express overall satisfaction with the Municipal Corporation's e-governance initiatives. Their primary expectation is for increased transparency, more accountability, and enhanced participation in the e-governance services provided by the Municipal Corporation.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that the overall mean perception of respondents towards the transparency dimension of e-governance in Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation is less favourable, ranging between 2 and 3 (specifically 2.94). This is not a positive sign for the establishment and development of e-governance. Transparency essentially entails open communication between citizens and the government (Abu-Shanab, Harb, & Al-Zoubi, 2013; Abu-Shanab, 2013). It signifies the unrestricted flow of information and its accessibility to users. Implementing this concept is particularly challenging in countries like India, which have a colonial history where governments are accustomed to concealing secrets and withholding information from the public (Wu, Yan, & Vyas, 2020; Samuel, Doctor, Christian, & Baradi, 2020; Kaur, 2022). Enhanced transparency leads to reduced corruption and greater accountability (Abu-Shanab, 2013). Access to information and transparent interactions empower citizens, enabling them to influence the delivery of services for their benefit and holding e-government institutions accountable for improved service delivery. Transparency in government operations builds trust among citizens in government institutions and strengthens democracy (Welch, Hinnant, & Moon, 2004, pp. 371-391). The finding confirms previous researches that have highlighted the issue of transparency in the delivery of public services by urban local bodies (Mohanty, 2005; Aijaz, 2007; Sharma, 2012; Siwach & Nillam, 2014; Ahluwalia, 2019).

A less favourable perception among users regarding the transparency dimension of e-governance services indicates that there are still significant transparency issues within the operation of the Municipal Corporation. The traditional nature of the government-citizen relationship serves as a barrier to the development of e-governance (National Institute of Urban Affairs, 2015; NITI Aayog, 2021).

The findings also highlight that the overall mean value of respondents' perceptions regarding the accountability dimension of e-governance is less favourable for the Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation, ranging between 2 and 3 (specifically 2.16). This is not a positive sign for the e-governance establishment and suggests a lack of accountability in the Municipal Corporation's service delivery. There is a strong and positive relationship between accountability

and public service delivery (Rana, Ali, Riaz, & Irfan, 2019, pp. 7-9). Municipal corporations should prioritize accountability within their organizations to improve the efficiency of public service delivery. The finding confirms previous research that has highlighted issues related to the lack of accountability in the delivery of public services by urban local bodies (Cavill & Sohail, 2003, pp. 235-244; Mohanty, 2005; Rao & Prasad, 2007; Aijaz, 2007; Rao N. , 2009; Venugopal & Yilmaz, 2009; Kluvers & Tippett, 2010; da Cruz & Marques, 2011; Sharma, 2012; Singh S., 2013; Mohan, Cutrell, & Parthasarathy, 2013; Siwach & Nillam, 2014; Boex, Malik, Brookins, & Edwards, 2016; Ahluwalia, 2019; NITI Aayog, 2021).

Based on the findings, it is evident that the overall mean value of the respondents' perception regarding the participation dimension of e-governance is unfavourable for the Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation. It falls within the range of 1 to 2, specifically at 1.52. This indicates a particularly poor performance by the Municipal Corporation. An unfavourable perception among users regarding the participation aspect of e-governance services indicates significant issues with people's engagement and involvement in the Municipal Corporation.

The findings confirm the results of previous researches that have emphasised the strong necessity for people's participation in Indian urban local bodies (Sivaramakrishnan, 2006; Aijaz, 2007; Rao & Prasad, 2007; Vaidya, 2009; Coelho, Kamath, & Vijaybaskar, 2011; Sharma, 2012; Singh S., 2013; Siwach & Nillam, 2014; Bhide, 2017; Ahluwalia, 2019; Das & Chattopadhyay, 2020). People's participation can foster better governance and enhance the interdependence between the government and its citizens (Kim, Halligan, Cho, Oh, & Eikenberry, 2005, pp. 646-654; Chun, Shulman, Sandoval, & Hovy, 2010).

The findings also indicate that the overall mean satisfaction level of respondents towards e-governance in the Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation is favourable, with a range between 3 and 4, (specifically at 3.32). This is a positive sign for the establishment and development of e-governance. Despite less favourable and unfavourable perceptions among users regarding dimensions like transparency, accountability, and participation within e-governance, the overall satisfaction level of users with the Municipal Corporation remains positive. This finding suggests that, even though users have high expectations from e-governance services that have not yet been fully met, they are satisfied with the Municipal Corporation's adoption of e-governance in service delivery. It implies that users believe that the service delivery will improve in the near future.

The higher overall satisfaction with e-governance services within the Municipal Corporation may be attributed to users' adaptability to the existing quality of public service delivery provided by the Municipal Corporation. Municipal Corporation users expect increased transparency, accountability, and participation

in e-governance processes. This suggests that citizens support their Municipal Corporation and are willing to engage in the governance process. Their satisfaction holds significant importance for the establishment of e-governance within Municipal Corporations. Previous studies have shown that citizen satisfaction with e-governance and trust in government are interconnected (Welch, Hinnant, & Moon, 2004, pp. 371-391). Municipal Corporations should leverage this user satisfaction and support to meet these expectations by ensuring transparency, accountability, and participation in their operations.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation has not yet fully achieved the goal of e-governance adaptation. This is evident from the less favourable perception of its users across all dimensions of e-governance services. However, overall user satisfaction with these services remains favourable, likely due to citizens' enthusiasm for the corporation's technological advancements meeting their expectations and aspirations. Based on these findings, we can draw several conclusions about how gender, age, education level, and sector of employment influence users' perceptions of three key dimensions of e-governance: transparency, accountability, and participation, as well as their overall satisfaction with e-governance services:

- Firstly, it is evident that gender plays a significant role in users' perceptions. Male users of Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation generally perceive more favourable values across all dimensions of e-governance.
- Secondly, age is another factor that impacts users' perceptions. Younger users, aged between 18 and 30 years, in Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation, tend to perceive higher levels of transparency, accountability, and participation.
- Thirdly, education level is a determining factor in users' perceptions of e-governance. Users with lower educational qualifications, typically at the intermediate level or below, perceive higher levels of transparency, accountability, and participation in the services provided by Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation.
- Lastly, the sector of employment also influences users' perceptions. Users employed in the public sector tend to perceive higher levels of transparency, while those in the private sector have more favourable perceptions of accountability and participation dimensions. The overall satisfaction with e-governance services is more favourably perceived by (i) male users (ii) users aged over 50 years, (iii) users with educational qualifications beyond post-graduation, and (iv) users employed in the private sector.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations can be made for the Thiruvananthapuram Municipal Corporation:

1. E-governance services should cater more to male users, particularly those in the 50-year age group, and should prioritize individuals with lower educational levels, specifically those at the intermediate level or below.
2. E-governance services should be tailored to meet the needs of users employed in the private sector.
3. To improve transparency, the Municipal Corporation should focus on capacity building for their officers and other employees through training, certificate courses on electronic governance, and other innovative techniques.
4. To enhance accountability, the Municipal corporation should streamline its processes for e-service requests, disposal, and monitoring by establishing monitoring and evaluation cells. They should also strengthen their record management systems and ensure timely delivery of services to citizens.
5. To encourage citizen participation, Municipal Corporations should first raise awareness about their e-governance services through mass media campaigns, social media, workshops, guidebook publications, and other innovative awareness programs. Subsequently, they should facilitate e-participation through their official websites and related portals. Special online participatory forums may also be created to enhance citizen engagement.

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